

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No5(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 330 sahifa,
22-may, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
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“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
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reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
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Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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SPHERES OF LANGUAGE USE

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Abstract: This article presents the idea that language can satisfy a wide range of communicative needs of individuals and society as a whole, and that different spheres of language use (or different languages, in the case of a non-monolingual society) are distinguished according to various spheres of human activity, such as production, education, science, culture, trade, and everyday life. A sphere of language use is defined as a sphere of extralinguistic reality characterized by the relative uniformity of communicative needs, for the satisfaction of which speakers deliberately select linguistic means and the rules for combining them. The article also substantiates the idea that, as a result of the selection of linguistic means and the rules governing their combination, a more or less stable tradition is formed within a particular linguistic community, linking a specific sphere of human activity with a particular linguistic code (subcode), namely an independent language or a subsystem of the national language.

Key words: language, activity, linguistics, communication, culture, reality, speech, science, human activity.

Annotsiya: Ushbu maqolada til shaxslar va umuman jamiyatning juda keng ko'lamdagi kommunikativ ehtiyojlarini qondira olishi hamda tildan foydalanishning turli sohalari (yoki monolingvistik bo'lmagan jamiyatda tillar) inson faoliyatining turli yo'nalishlari – ishlab chiqarish, ta'lim, fan, madaniyat, savdo, kundalik hayot va boshqalarga muvofiq ravishda farqlanishi haqidagi fikrlar bayon etilgan. Tildan foydalanish sohasi kommunikativ ehtiyojlarning nisbiy bir xilligi bilan tavsiflanadigan ekstralingvistik voqelik sohasi bo'lib, ushbu ehtiyojlarni qondirish uchun so'zlovchilar lingvistik vositalarni hamda ularni o'zaro birlashtirish qoidalarini aniq tanlaydilar. Maqolada, shuningdek, lingvistik vositalarni tanlash va ularni o'zaro birlashtirish qoidalari natijasida inson faoliyatining muayyan sohasini ma'lum bir lingvistik kod (subkod), ya'ni mustaqil til yoki milliy tilning quyi tizimi bilan bog'lovchi nisbatan barqaror an'ana shakllanishi haqidagi asosli fikrlar ham keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, harakat, lingvistika, muloqot, madaniyat, voqelik, nutq, fan, faoliyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены идеи о том, что язык способен удовлетворять весьма широкий спектр коммуникативных потребностей отдельных лиц и общества в целом, а различные сферы использования языка (или языков, если речь идёт о немоналингвистическом обществе) различаются в соответствии с различными сферами человеческой деятельности – производством, образованием, наукой, культурой, торговлей, повседневной жизнью и т. д. Сфера использования языка представляет собой сферу экстралингвистической реальности, характеризующуюся относительной однородностью коммуникативных потребностей, для удовлетворения которых говорящие целенаправленно выбирают языковые средства и правила их сочетания друг с другом. В статье также обоснована идея о том, что в результате выбора языковых средств и правил их сочетания формируется более или менее устойчивая традиция (для данного языкового сообщества), связывающая определённую сферу человеческой деятельности с определённым языковым кодом (субкодом) – самостоятельным языком или подсистемой национального языка.

Ключевые слова: язык, действие, лингвистика, коммуникация, культура, реальность, речь, наука, деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

Language can serve a very broad range of communicative needs of individuals and society as a whole. In accordance with different areas of human activity—production, education, science, culture, trade, everyday life, and others—different spheres of language use (or different languages, in the case of a multilingual society) are distinguished. A sphere of language use is an area of extra-linguistic reality characterized by a relative homogeneity of communicative needs, for the satisfaction of which speakers select specific linguistic means and rules for their combination. As a result of this selection, a more or less stable tradition is formed within a linguistic community, correlating a particular sphere of human activity with a specific linguistic code (subcode)—either an

independent language or a subsystem of a national language. Thus, in medieval Europe, Latin served as the primary means of communication in worship and science, while other spheres of activity were served by the corresponding national languages and their subsystems. In Russia, the role of religious communication for a long time belonged to Church Slavonic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Outstanding scholars of the first half of the 20th century, such as I. A. Baudouin de Courtenay, E. D. Polivanov, L. P. Yakubinsky, V. M. Zhirmunsky, B. A. Larin, A. M. Selishchev, and G. O. Vinokur in Russia; F. Bruno, A. Meillet, P. Lafargue, and M. Cohen in France; C. Bally and A. Sachtet in Switzerland; J. Vendryes in Belgium; and B. Havránek and W. Mathesius in Czechoslovakia, formulated a number of ideas without which modern sociolinguistics could not exist.

For example, C. Bally proposed the idea that all language resources are distributed among spheres of communication and that the division of communication into spheres is largely socially determined. Russian and Czech linguists developed the concept of social differentiation within a single national language depending on the social status of its speakers.

E. D. Polivanov argued that the pace of linguistic evolution depends on the pace of social development and that language development generally lags behind social change.

B. A. Larin extended methods used in the study of rural dialects to the investigation of urban speech.

E. D. Polivanov substantiated the need for social dialectology alongside territorial dialectology.

B. A. Larin, V. M. Zhirmunsky, and D. S. Likhachev emphasized the importance of studying jargons, argot, and other non-codified forms of language in order to understand the internal structure of a national language system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the modern Pamir region, one of the Pamir languages—the unwritten Shughni language—is used primarily in family and everyday communication among the Shughni people living in Tajikistan. In official situations, as well as when communicating with outsiders, speakers usually resort to Tajik or Russian. Languages and their subsystems can be distributed flexibly across spheres of activity: one language or subsystem may predominate in a certain sphere, while the use of elements from other languages or subsystems is also permitted. For example, in family communication among residents of a modern Russian village, the local dialect usually predominates, and it is also commonly used during agricultural work. However, under contemporary conditions, a pure dialect is rarely preserved. It is mainly retained among representatives of the older generation in rural areas. In the speech of most speakers, the dialect is significantly influenced by elements of the literary language and colloquial speech. Similarly, in Belarus, the Belarusian language is actively used in the humanities, which is encouraged by official state policy, although elements of closely related languages may also appear in this sphere. In the manufacturing sector, despite governmental support for the national language, Russian predominates in specialized terminology, technical documentation, and professional communication among specialists. Nevertheless, the use of Belarusian is not prohibited. The term “communication” has many meanings. For example, it is used in the expression “mass communication,” referring to the press, radio, and television. In technology, the term denotes communication lines, while the Internet represents one of the most powerful forms of modern communication.

In sociolinguistics, communication is understood as both speech and non-speech interaction. The foreign-language term “communication” is particularly convenient because it easily forms derivatives necessary for describing different aspects of interaction, such as communicative situation, communicants (participants in communication), and other related concepts. Communication may be verbal or non-verbal. For instance, communication in certain sports, such as basketball, football, or volleyball, does not necessarily include a significant verbal component, or it includes only minimal verbal signals such as “Pass!” or “Take it!” Likewise, not all physical labor requires verbal interaction. In noisy workshops—such as stamping, assembly, or foundry workshops—spoken words are often impractical; nevertheless, workers continue to communicate through gestures and other non-verbal means. However, a considerably larger proportion of human interaction occurs through speech, since language is primarily intended for communication. These forms of communication are of primary interest to sociolinguists.

A communicative situation has a specific structure consisting of the following components:

- 1) the speaker (sender);
- 2) the listener (receiver);

- 3) the relationship between the speaker and the listener;
- 4) the tone of communication (formal, neutral, or friendly);
- 5) the purpose of communication;
- 6) the means of communication (language or its subsystem—dialect, style, as well as paralinguistic means such as gestures and facial expressions);
- 7) the mode of communication (oral or written, direct or remote); and
- 8) the place of communication.

These components are regarded as situational variables. A change in any of them leads to a transformation of the communicative situation and consequently to variations in the linguistic means and communicative behavior used by participants. For example, communication between a judge and a witness in a courtroom is characterized by a much greater degree of formality than communication between the same individuals outside a court hearing. In this case, the place of communication changes while most other situational variables remain constant. A judge's questioning of a witness in order to obtain biographical information presupposes a question-and-answer format of interaction, accompanied by the corresponding syntactic features of dialogue, such as elliptical statements and the repetition of certain elements of the question by the respondent.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A judge's request for a witness to reproduce testimony given during the preliminary investigation presupposes a predominantly monologic form of speech on the part of the judge and only a confirming or denying response from the witness. In this case, the purpose of communication changes, whereas all other situational variables remain unchanged. Speech communication, speech behavior, and speech act are all directly related to the process of verbal interaction. The first term is regarded as a synonym for "speech communication." It is important to emphasize that both concepts denote a two-way process, namely the interaction between individuals during communication. In contrast, the term "speech behavior" highlights the one-sided nature of the process. It refers to the properties and characteristics that distinguish the speech and verbal reactions of one of the participants in a communicative situation, either the speaker (sender) or the listener (addressee). The term "speech behavior" is particularly useful for describing monologic forms of speech, such as lectures, speeches at meetings, public rallies, and similar communicative situations. However, this term is insufficient for analyzing dialogue because, in dialogic interaction, it is essential to reveal the mechanisms of mutual verbal actions rather than merely describe the speech behavior of each participant separately.

CONCLUSION

However, in small linguistic communities, such as families where communication is direct and predominantly oral, there may exist not one but two languages, for example, Russian and Kazakh. In some cases, there may even be more languages involved. Families of modern Russian emigrants, for instance, are known to use several languages in intra-family communication. Thus, the concept of "speech communication" includes the concept of "speech behavior," which demonstrates the close interrelation between these linguistic categories.

References:

1. Znadvorova, A. V. "Reflection of Social Differentiation of Language in the Linguistic Life of Small Groups (Based on the Example of a Family)" // *Modern Russian: Social and Functional Differentiation*. Moscow, 2003. pp. 277-340.
2. Znadvorova, A. V. "Speech Communication in Small Social Groups (Based on the Example of a Family)" // *Modern Russian: Social and Functional Differentiation*. Moscow, 2003. pp. 381-402.
3. Krysin, L. P. "Sociolinguistic Problems in the Contact of Closely Related Languages" // *Typology of Bilingualism and Multilingualism in Belarus* / Ed. A. N. Bulyko, L. P. Krysin. Minsk, 1999. pp. 3-11.
4. Zibatov, L. // *Russian Linguistics*. 1997.
5. Lehfeldt, W. // *Zeitschrift für Slawische Philologie*. 1997. Hf. 1.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №5(5)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.